

Enhanced MMSE-based LMS Optimization of Analog Feed-Forward Equalizer for 50G-PON

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Abstract We propose a novel algorithm for analog FFE for 50G-PON, overcoming challenges in equalization. A novel method models and optimizes FFE responses and coefficients, improving optical transmission integrity. Results demonstrate significant BER reduction compared to FFE-free, highlighting potential for ASP adoption in 50G-PON. ©2024 The Author(s)

Introduction

The 50 Gigabit capable Passive Optical Network (50G-PON) is the last finalized International Telecommunication Union (ITU-T) Passive Optical Network (PON) specification^[1]. It proposes a Downstream (DS) bitrate at 50 Gbit/s, with a wavelength centered at 1342 ± 2 nm and three Upstream (US) bitrates: 12.5, 25 and 50 Gbit/s at 1286 ± 2 nm^[2] in Non-Return-to-Zero On-Off-Keying (NRZ-OOK). The PON architecture is presented on Fig. 1. The Optical Line Termination (OLT) is placed in a Central Office (CO) and is connected to Optical Network Unit (ONU) by a point-to-multipoint topology with a splitting ratio up to 128 terminations over 20 km max. From PON's legacy, a signal is sent continuously in DS while for the US the Burst Mode (BM) is imposed, i.e. each ONU has a window allocated to transmit data.

Fig. 1: Architecture of the PON.

The 50G-PON channel is primarily constrained by the limited Bandwidth (BW) of the low-cost transmitter and receiver (such as 25G class receivers) used for cost reasons, but also by the noise and the Chromatic Dispersion (CD), which can cause distortions, InterSymbol Interference (ISI). Equalization techniques were introduced to mitigate those effects, for the first time of PON specifications but have been studied for a long time^[3]. The Feed-Forward Equalizer (FFE) is a common equalization solution which aims at mitigating the effects of ISI in a telecommunication system by pre-emphasizing the received signal based on past transmitted symbols, thereby enhancing the signal's integrity and improving overall

data transmission performance. Since the first definition of 50G-PON, Digital Signal Processing (DSP) has been proposed and has always been the subject of several research studies. In^{[4]-[7]}, the authors manage to equalize with low complexity, in the sense that they're looking for a solution that's high-performance, energy-efficient and inexpensive. Although the DSP implementation of FFE can deliver high-performance results, the problem with this solution is that it requires more energy resources than Analog Signal Processing (ASP). Indeed, analog FFE (FFE-ASP) has also been studied in PON^{[8]-[10]}. Although this solution is cheaper and less energy-hungry than the previous one, the adaptation of taps' weight over time remains a challenging task due to two main factors. Firstly, the search for the optimal setting of the analog filter coefficients proves to be a tricky problem due the large number of combinations between taps values. Secondly, ASP requires consideration of the device imperfections, including the limited bandwidths of each FFE tap and the non-linearity of taps of the FFE-ASP.

This paper proposes a new method for optimizing the parameter settings of a FFE-ASP filter using a Minimum Mean Square Error (MMSE) approach with the Least Mean Squares (LMS) algorithm. The technique proposed in this study involves an implicit trade-off between amplifying channel noise and mitigating ISI. The frequency response of each coefficient of the FFE is taken into account, in order to take care of the ASP special features.

Fig. 2: Analog FFE architecture modeling.

Fig. 3: a) Experimental setup, b) Frequency and c) Impulse responses of each tap for a given value.

FFE-ASP modeling and MMSE algorithm

In order to assess the performance of our algorithm, the following work consists in two parts: the first part presents the algorithm in details, while the second focuses on the experimental results. Both consider the same hardware FFE, having the following characteristics: 6-taps FFE-ASP with a delay between each tap of 7.5 ps. Each equalizer tap can be adjusted to 255 different positions. As a result, 255^6 combinations are possible. The analog nature of the FFE needs to make several considerations: the first is that there is a leak at each tap (part of the signal passing through the taps switched off), which needs to be taken into account when setting coefficient values. Secondly, it has been observed that the impulse responses of each tap, obtained from the measured S-parameters, it has been observed that the impulse responses of each tap are not identical for the same setting (tap number k being set to a given value and the others to zero) in terms of amplitudes and the BW is limited, see Fig. 3b and 3c. As a result, the impulse responses $h_{j_k}[n]$ (which means tap number k with its corresponding setting j between -127 to +127) are normalized by its root square of its energy, see Eq. 1:

$$h_{j_k, norm}[n] = \frac{h_{j_k}[n]}{\|h_{j_k}[n]\|} \quad (1)$$

Thus, the FFE-ASP is then modeled (see Eq. 2 and Fig. 2) as a linear combination of 6 normalized impulse responses $h_{j_k, norm}[n]$ with coefficients c_{j_k} (with $c_{j_k} = \|h_{j_k}[n]\|$) multiplied by an Automatic Gain Control (AGC) ($G[n]$). When the value of index j is greater than or equal to 0, we invert the values of c_{j_k} and $h_{j_k, norm}$ so that coefficients can be updated using the gradient algorithm. The objective is to find the optimal solution of normalized impulse responses ($h_{j_k, norm}[n]$) with its associated coefficients (c_{j_k}) and the AGC ($G[n]$).

$$h_{FFE}[n] = G[n] \times \sum_{k=0}^5 c_{j_k} \times h_{j_k, norm}[n] \quad (2)$$

With the use of the c_{j_k} coefficients, the problem consists in a classical Mean Squared Error (MSE) minimization problem, see Eq. 3. Thus, the optimization problem is expressed as the search for the optimal values of $c_{j_k}[n]$ by selecting the optimal j setting for each tap number $k \in \{0, 1, \dots, 5\}$ by using the Normalized LMS (NLMS) algorithm^[11] (for its adaptation capacity). It provides the updated

values of $c_{j_k}[n]$, see Eq. 4. In our case, with the particularity that the c_{j_k} coefficients correspond to discrete variables and not to continuous variables as usual, so each time the new one is calculated, we take the closest one (an quantization error is therefore added).

$$J = \min_{\substack{k \in \llbracket 0, 5 \rrbracket \\ j \in \llbracket -127, 127 \rrbracket}} \mathbb{E}(\hat{a}[n] - h_{FFE}[n] * x[n])^2 \quad (3)$$

$$\forall k \in \llbracket 0, 5 \rrbracket, c_{j_k}[n+1] = c_{j_k}[n] + \mu \frac{e[n]z[n]}{\hat{\sigma}_z^2} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{with } z[n] = h_{FFE}[n] * x[n]$$

$\hat{\sigma}_z^2$ is the estimation of the variance of z . The AGC ($G[n]$) is adapted with a simple LMS with an adaptation step of $\mu = 4 \times 10^{-10}$. The proposed approach assumes quasi-invariance of impulse responses for local variations in c_{j_k} . Therefore, if the index j of coefficient c_{j_k} varies slightly for tap k , the response $h_{j_k, norm}[n]$ changes minimally, with the only changing parameter being the value of coefficient c_{j_k} .

Experimental Setup

The experimental setup is presented on Fig. 3a. A NRZ-OOK electrical Pseudo Random Binary Sequence (PRBS) of length $2^{31}-1$ is generated at 50 Gbit/s by a Pulse Pattern Generator (PPG) with a 600 mVpp amplitude. A 23 dB gain electrical amplifier is used to drive the Externally Modulated Laser (EML) having a 3 dB BW of 55 GHz and a wavelength of 1341 nm (CD of ≈ 4 ps/nm.km⁻¹ in the Standard Single Mode Fiber (SSMF)). The emitter's chipset is composed of a Distributed FeedBack laser (DFB), integrated with an Electro-Absorption Modulator (EAM) and a Semiconductor Optical Amplifier (SOA) cascaded. The output signal has an Extinction Ratio (ER) of 7.12 dB and an optical power of -2 dBm. 0 or 10 km of SSMF are added before a Variable Optical Attenuator (VOA) to introduce CD. A coupler is added with a branch connected to a powermeter ("PWM" in Fig. 3) to measured the Received Optical Power (ROP), while the other branch is connected to an isolator and then to a Positive Intrinsic Negative (PIN) photodiode with an Optical-Electrical (OE) BW of 40 GHz. To emulate the low-pass filtering effect of the low-cost components within the transmitting chain, a Bessel Radio Frequency (RF) filter with a cutoff frequency (F_c) of 13 GHz is inserted. This choice was made for reasons of practicality and material availability: in the ITU-T context, the

Fig. 4: Electrical eye diagram at the receiver side in BtB **a)** without & **b)** with FFE. Electrical eye diagram at the receiver side with 10 km of SSMF **c)** without & **d)** with FFE.

use of class 25G Avalanche PhotoDiode (APD) with about 18 GHz bandwidth is preferred^[1]. The signal ((1) Fig. 3) goes through the FFE-ASP previously presented (6 taps, 7.5 ps spacing) to compensate the channel BW limitation and CD. Eye diagrams and Bit Error Rate (BER) are captured at FFE input and output (on (1) and (2) on Fig. 3) respectively with a Digital Communication Analyzer (DCA) and an Error Detector (ED).

The signal is captured with a Real-Time Oscilloscope (RTO) (sampling rate of 100 GSa/s & 33 GHz BW) at the output of the Bessel filter ((2) Fig. 3). After this acquisition, the signal is captured with 2 samples per symbol (after resampled for 3 samples per symbol). At time t_0 , the first 6 samples are multiplied with the previously initialized impulse responses and then multiplied with the coefficient c_{jk} , summed and multiplied by the AGC (G on Fig. 2). The decision ($\hat{a}[n]$ in Eq. 3) at the boundaries of the decision circuit is made on one of the three phases.

Fig. 5: Global frequency response of the FFE.

Results

Fig. 4a and 4c show the eye diagrams (obtained with a DCA) before the FFE in Back-to-Back (BtB) and 10 km of fiber respectively. We can see that the signal is damaged by the presence of the ISIs (mainly due to the 13 GHz filter) as expected. A BER of 10^{-4} was observed in BtB and 10^{-3} for 10 km of fiber before the FFE. After asymptotic convergence of c_{jk} coefficients using the proposed algorithm, we were able to measure the MSE as a function of the time, see Eq. 3. The MSE, calculated in a window of 64 samples, is shown in Fig. 6e (BtB). The MSE obtained is around -

Fig. 6: Temporal evolution of the MSE.

11.5 dB. When the optimum solution has been obtained, the indexes are retrieved and entered into the analog FFE. When this procedure is carried out for 0 and 10 km of fiber, we look at the eye diagrams in Fig. 4b and 4d. We can see that the eye diagrams are much better, enabling the receiver to facilitate decisions at the boundaries of the decision circuit. After ASP, we obtain a BER of 7×10^{-9} and 2×10^{-6} in BtB and for 10 km of fiber respectively. This confirms that the algorithm managed to optimize the FFE parameters in order to improve the transmitted signal's quality. Furthermore, Fig. 5 shows the overall frequency response after finding the indexes. It can be seen that the overall response of the FFE does indeed increase the high frequencies.

Conclusions

In this study, we addressed the challenge of the MMSE optimization of the FFE-ASP for 50G-PON. The advantage of ASP is that it's less expensive and requires fewer resources than DSP. Due to the analog nature of the FFE-ASP, its optimization needs to take care of the individual tap limited pulse response. In this study, we presented a new method based on the MMSE technique for ASP of a received signal. An FFE-ASP has been modeled to facilitate the search for the optimal solution of normalized impulse responses and the associated coefficients for each tap. This work was validated thanks to an NRZ-OOK optical transmission at 50 Gbit/s in BtB and with 10 km of fiber. The results showed that we were able to eliminate ISIs and reduce BER (BtB: 10^{-4} to 7×10^{-9} and 10 km: 10^{-3} to 2×10^{-6}).

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